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Measurement of Boron Concentration In Water Wells Samples Of Al-Diwaniyan Governorates-Iraq Using SSNTDs Techniques

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Abstract

Consumption of food and drinking water which is polluted by boron, may lead to many health hazards for the consumers. Thus, the concentration of boron in food particles must be determined. In this current study, Drinking water samples were collected from different places of Basrah in Iraq, as well as the Water well samples were collected from several places of Diwaniya in Iraq. The detection of boron levels was carried out by examining the collected water samples using SSNTDs method. The obtained results of boron levels were between 4.11 ppm (alsuniya 2 well belt) and 0.53 ppm (Eastern Hamza 4 well). The findings of this study have been compared with the International standard values and previously published studies. These findings can be used to create rules by the Iraqi government to reduce the radioactive contamination of drinking water in Basrah in Iraq. This current research has shown that, the 24 surface water samples have boron lesser than the international standard values. Hence, the level of boron in Basrah drinking water is normal. However, there is a possibility of severe pollution problems of boron in near future. Thus, more studies must be done in the future.

Key words: SSNTDs Techniques; Boron; Track density; CR-39 track

Introduction

Boron is a naturally-occurring element which is found in rocks, soil and water. It is classified as a non-metallic element. Its atomic weight is 10.81 while its atomic number is 5. Boron has two isotopes: boron-10 which has abundance of 19.8% and boron-11 that has abundance of 80.2% [9]. Boron level in the Earth's crust is estimated to be less than 10 ppm whereas its level is found to be as high as 100 ppm in places which has higher level of boron presence [17]. Solid State Nuclear Track Detectors (SSNTDs) of different materials are important for investigations in basic science and technology [6]. SSNTDs are commonly applied in radiation protection and environmental radiation observation. The theory of SSNTDs was realized several years ago, the elementary principles were explained by Thaer M Salman et al [13] and wide explanation can be found in Durrani et al. [4]. The details of alpha particle detection were reported by Nikezic [5]. Therefore, some aspects of interest are only highlighted in this current study.

Depending on the chemical treatment (called etching) and observation method, there are basically two requirements: the range

and energy deposition of the particle should be adequate [3]. This paper characterizes the initial results from boron level detection data that was collected from several locations of Al-Diwaniya in Iraq. The main goal is to examine the multifaceted changes and the interactions with the water flow and estimate the amount of hazards brought by these waters. In fact, the study area is located inside the Al-Diwaniya Governorate. The boron chemical structure is illustrated in Figure 1. Solid State Nuclear Track Detectors SSNTDs of different materials are important for investigations in basic science and technology [14]. SSNTDs are commonly applied in radiation protection and environmental radiation observation. The theory of SSNTDs was realized several years ago, the elementary principles were explained by Somogyi [12, 2]. The details of the alpha particle detection are significant from BNCT attitude [10]. For the 10 BNC reaction to happen, it involves a sample containing, an even at ppb amongst the identified boron compounds, numerous hundreds are engaged in today's applications and on a rising level, 10 B, a source fixed for radio activity with the thermal or minor neutron energy (0.025 eV or lower) and by a reaction fragment identifying

Figure 1. Chemical Structures of Some Boron Compounds

method. The reaction occurrence is by the association of a neutron interaction with a boron nucleus, after which it breaks up into two fragments of the $10\text{B}+n$ compound nucleus (to leave a short time in the order of picoseconds). The two fragments proceed, obtaining the kinetic energy because of the strong Coulomb field moving in reverse direction underneath the law of momentum conservation, which is manufactured by the indicated procedure:

This reaction happens with the diverse branching relationship: The First reaction has a relatively smaller frequency occurrence (6.1 %) but it has an improved reaction with fewer photons and therefore the induced damage causes a higher "Linear Energy Transfer" (LET) or dE/dx . The other reaction, with an advanced occurrence is accompanied by a 0.48 MeV photon. If the alpha particle (4He^+) immigrates the sample surface, with an adequate kinetic energy, then it can be identified for e.g. by the nuclear track methods. The alpha particle fingerprint assumed by an appropriate identifying substantial, offers information on the boron occurrence and it is quite predictable as a powerful methodical technique for boron studies. This study denotes the primary results from the concentration of boron quantity data that was collected from several places in Al-Diwaniya city. Our main goal is to explore the complex exchanges and interactions with the water flow and estimate the amount of hazards brought by these waters. The area of study is placed inside Al-Diwaniya/Iraq, see Figure 2.

Figure 2. Diwaniya Governorate, Dots represent the places where Samples taken from, Numbering in Station Number

Material and Methods

In the Al-Diwaniya governorate, the samples from 24 stations and locations were collected during May 2018. The measurements of

boron concentration in soil were achieved by passive method which is called SSNTDs. CR-39 (1x1 cm) films which are common types of SSNTDs are used in this measurement. One milliliter from various boron concentrations is released to the identical area of the CR-39 track detector and then it is dried. After that, the typical samples are irradiated to a source of thermal neutron for the equal period of time (7 days). A nuclear reaction of type $10\text{B}(n, \alpha)^7\text{Li}$ has arisen the alpha particles which are released with an energy of 2.31 MeV. This energy can make an appropriate track in CR-39 plastic detector. The samples which after being irradiated, are cleaned in distilled water, and then etched in a solution of 6.25 N (Normality) NaOH at 60°C temperature for 6 hours (etching time), by applying a bath held at a fixed temperature. The track diameters and track density have been achieved using a transmission optical microscope and an appropriate calibration curve is applied to measure the boron concentration. The pieces of each of the detector sets are exposed with neutrons that are emitted from Am-Be.

Irradiation of the samples

The pellets (water samples of well) are shielded with CR-39 detector and placed in a plate of paraffin wax at a space of 5 cm from the neutron source Am-Be, with the flux of thermal neutron ($5 \times 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ S}^{-1}$) as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Soil Samples and Detector Irradiation in Front of the Thermal Neutron Source.

Chemical etching and Microscopic Scanning

After the radioactivity time of 7 days, the CR-39 detectors are detached and etched in a 6.25 N aqueous solution of NaOH maintained at 70°C for 6 hours, which is the normal employed etching time [11]. The detectors are rinsed with distilled water and then dried in the air. The tracks verified in CR-39 detectors are counted by applying optical microscope at a magnification of 400 X. The density of the tracks in the detectors is calculated by using the indicated formula:

$$\rho = \frac{N_{av}}{A} \quad (2)$$

Where ρ is the Track density (Track/mm²), N is the average of total tracks and A is the area of field view.

Calibration Curve for Soil Sample

For the calibration, the curve plot between the standards for various boron solutions of identified concentrations has been set from 2 ppm to 1 ppm for the calibration of our study and the density of track by applying neutron induced radiography that is constructed on the principle of the solid state nuclear detectors SSNTDs CR-39. The concentration of boron are determined by the comparison between

the track densities registered on the detectors of the samples and that of the standard samples from the Regression equation: $y = 2767.67 + 352.715 * X$, $R^2 = 0.97354$. A linear calibration as shown in Figure 4 was observed, followed by the calculation of the slope factor. The results are experimented in (mg B/l).

Figure 4. Track Density Visa Boron Concentration For Standard Boron Samples

Result and Discussion

Table 1 represents the track density and Boron concentration samples done by the CR -39 detectors. The water samples of the wells collected from fifteen locations distributed in different sites of al-shanaafia, al-shaamia, al-suniya, Afak, Nufer, Al Badair, aldighara, Sumer and Eastern Hamza districts in the Al-Diwaniya governorate. Figure 5 shows the relationship between Boron concentration and the numbers of location for the soil sample.

Figure 5. Boron Concentrations as a Function of Number Location

For the measurement of boron concentration level, water samples for the wells Table 1 and Figure 5. The results for these 30 samples are categorized into 30 locations, from S1 to S30, shown in Figure 5. Boron content was found to be the maximum of 4.117 ppm in (alsuniya 2) wells belt and to be the minimum of 0.531 ppm as recorded in (Eastern Hamza 4) belt. Out of the 30 water samples of the wells, 1 sample recorded higher beginning from 4.117 ppm, while the 7 water samples of the wells beginning from 2.013 ppm to 2.565 ppm, while the 16 water samples of the wells beginning from 1.073 ppm to 1.853 ppm, while the 6 water samples of the wells beginning from 0.531 ppm to 0.967 ppm than the prescribed WHO limit 0.5 ppm.

Table 1. Boron Concentration in the water in Al-Diwaniya wells using SSNTDS method

Site Number	Site Name	Tracks Density (Tracks/Mm ²)	Boron Concentrations(Ppm)
S1	alshanaafia 1	3146.352	1.073
S2	alshanaafia 2	3102.658	0.949
S3	alshanaafia 3	3232.83	1.318
S4	alshaamia 1	3505.973	2.093
S5	alshaamia 2	3506.361	2.094
S6	alshaamia 3	3517.752	2.126
S7	alshaamia 4	3164.5449	1.125
S8	alshaamia 5	3172.749	1.148
S9	alsuniya 1	3164.558	1.125
S10	alsuniya 2	4220.02	4.117
S11	alsuniya 3	3302.923	1.517
S12	Afak 1	3476.809	2.013
S13	Afak 2	3421.261	1.853
S14	Afak 3	3239.202	1.336
S15	Nufer 1	3413.949	1.832
S16	Nufer 2	3219.176	1.280
S17	Nufer 3	3487.731	2.041
S18	Al Badair1	3013.065	0.695
S19	Al Badair2	3109.028	0.967
S20	Al Badair3	3633.359	2.454
S21	aldighara 1	3191.867	1.202
S22	aldighara 2	3672.575	2.565
S23	aldighara 3	3180.943	1.171
S24	Sumer 1	3219.176	1.280
S25	Sumer 2	3357.54	1.672
S26	Sumer 3	3213.714	1.264
S27	Eastern Hamza 1	3075.569	0.872
S28	Eastern Hamza 2	3196.638	1.216
S29	Eastern Hamza 3	2997.064	0.650
S30	Eastern Hamza 4	2955.191	0.531

In 1993, the WHO produced a health-based Guideline of 0.3 mg/L for boron. This value was primarily raised to 0.5 mg/L in 1998. Moreover in 2000, it was obvious to stop using the guideline of 0.5 mg/L until the data from continuing the research development that may make alterations for the present view of boron toxicity or boron treatment technology [16, 15]. The European Union established a value of 1.0 mg/L for boron in 1998 for the quality of water intended for human consumption [7, 1]. New Zealand has established a drinking water standard for boron of 1.4 mg/L [8]. The safety of boron concentration in Canada according to (IMAC) is 5 mg/L. The Canadians have established this value on the basis of practical treatment technology. Today, it is impossible to decrease boron concentrations to less than 5 mg/L according to inadequate technologies. They will review this IMAC periodically as new data becomes available.

Conclusion

Well soils are in many rural localities in rural areas and are existent in the Al-Diwaniya Governorate-Iraq. The analytical results of chemical soil analysis has revealed the presence of Boron in the New Zealand with the limit of 1.4 ppm and IMAC 5 ppm, with a variation between (0.53 - 4.11) ppm. The values of Boron concentration are small and within the natural limits in most of the sample from the water samples of the wells. The correlation factor of 97.35%, between the boron concentration of standard samples and Track density (track/m²) of the samples in water samples of the wells, are in a very good correlation. Access to safe water of the wells is essential to the human well-being and is a key to public health issue.

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